

Cross Sectional Study

Prevalence of Chronic Kidney Disease in Type 2 Diabetes Patients in India: An Observational, Cross-sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background Diabetes mellitus or type 2 diabetes, is becoming a major concern of health threats for the people globally. This is resulting in affecting kidneys and thus resulting in chronic kidney disease. The cases of chronic kidney disease due to diabetes are increasing globally. As far as the number of patients of type two diabetes in India is concerned, it has been named as the "diabetes capital of the world".

Objective The main objective of the study is to analyze the prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) amongst patients having type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in India.

Methods An observational cross-sectional study was carried out in Dr PDMMC hospital, Amravati, Maharashtra, India during the period between September 2018 to April, 2019. One thousand four hundred fifty patients were taken into consideration for the scope of the study. Patients with a diagnosis of T1DM, acute kidney injury, symptomatic urinary tract infection, history of hematuria, known renal transplant, on maintenance dialysis, participation in any interventional study within past three months and pregnant women were excluded from the study.

Results The mean age of the study population was found out to be around 53.5 years. The mean duration of T2DM was 102 months. In the course of data analysis, nearly 43% of the total participants were reported to be affected by dyslipidemia and hypertension. It was studied in the research that a very low percentage of the patients were affected by microvascular and macrovascular complications.

Conclusion The study adds valuable literature that identifies the level of renal dysfunction in patients suffering from T2DM. It was also analyzed that the majority of the patients having T2DM suffered from chronic kidney disease in India.

Key words: Dyslipidemia, hypertension, diabetes.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus or type 2 diabetes is becoming a major concern of health threats for the people globally. This is resulting in affecting kidneys and thus resulting in chronic kidney disease. The cases of chronic kidney disease due to diabetes are increasing globally. As far as the number of patients of type two diabetes in India is concerned, it has been named as the "diabetes capital of the world". This has been proved by the WHO statistics. In the year 2015,

the number of type 2 diabetes patients in India were nearly 69 million^[1]. Further, as per the calculation, it has been estimated that by the year 2030, the number of type 2 diabetes patients would rise to as high as 98 million in India. These figures are alarming as type 2 diabetes is not only for diabetic patients but also invites the other diseases. The patients suffering from type 2 diabetes are prone to microvascular and macrovascular complications that include kidney disease.

CKD is identified when the estimated glomerular filtration rate [eGFR] < 60 mL/min/1.73 m² or urine albumin-creatinine ratio > 30 mg/g. This signifies that in the busy modern world, type 2 diabetes is becoming the leading cause of end-stage renal failure. It has also been analyzed by most of the researchers that 30% of the patients having diabetic nephropathy^[2]. Further, it has been established that the remaining patients generally suffer from severe cardiovascular disease. All the patients suffering type 2 develop microalbuminuria and, subsequently, proteinuria. Hence, the level of albuminuria is a major risk factor for the patients suffering from type 2 diabetes, and thus they must go in for a yearly test of microalbuminuria in order to diagnose the chances of any kidney disease. This signifies the fact that the type 2 DM demands life-long care, monitoring and management. If not managed and monitored timely, it is sure that the type 2 DM would lead to end-stage chronic kidney disease^[3].

OBJECTIVE

The main objective of the study is to analyze the prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) amongst patients having type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in India.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Various studies have been conducted by the researchers on the reasons regarding the role of type 2 diabetes in the development of chronic kidney diseases. The following studies have been conducted by the researchers:

As per the study conducted by Bchir et al. (2004), it has been estimated that there is an increase in the number of cases of diabetes around the globe. The spread of T2DM patients is so aggressive in India as well as other parts of the world that it can be termed as an epidemic. It costs heavily on the life of humans, along with disturbing the economic status as well. Another major consequence of the rising patients is that the chances of chronic health disease rise manifolds. Further, owing to this disease, the morbidity of patients increases manifolds. This disease can be easily transmitted from pregnant women to their unborn child, and thus, it remains with them for their entire life. Hence, the study suggested that a global initiative is required to be taken so that the entire human race can fight this epidemic easily^[4].

Further, a study by Atkins (2005) propagated the epidemiology of chronic kidney diseases and as the findings of the study revealed that T2DM is one of the most frightening factors leading to CKD. It was revealed through the study that T2DM has contributed significantly in the morbidity and mortality of the patients worldwide. The study found that nearly 25% of the income of Indian families is spent on diabetes treatment. Also, the report found that in the budget for national health care Diabetes covers around 15%. Further, it is estimated that by 2025, \$150 billion would be invested globally for the medication of diabetes^[5].

Another study by Mohan et al. (2007) mentioned that India is speedily becoming the hub of diabetes in the world. As per the study, it was found that the onset age of the disease has reduced manifolds. It means that the younger generation is getting more affected by T2DM. This is building up health issues for the future generation at an early age. The study further concluded that regular checkups and early diagnosis could avoid the risk of T2DM, and thus, chronic kidney disease. This would help to reduce the cases of chronic kidney failure resulting from T2DM. Thus, postponing the early onset of the disease is the most appropriate way of avoiding CKD^[6].

Heerspink and Zeeuw, (2011) concluded that even after following lifestyle changes and various other nutritional changes, the people suffering from T2DM have to take medication at

all point of time. Continuous medication and monitoring is a must in the T2DM as it is the major factor contributing to renal and cardiovascular complications. The disease leads to multi-organ failure, thus leading to CKD leading to death or life dependent on dialysis^[7].

Also, as per Crofford et al. (2012), suggested that intensive therapy effectively delays the onset and slows the progression of diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy in patients with IDDM^[8].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

An observational cross-sectional study was carried out in Dr PDMMC hospital, Amravati, Maharashtra, India during the period between September 2018 to April, 2019. One thousand four hundred fifty patients were taken into consideration for the scope of the study. Patients with a diagnosis of T1DM, acute kidney injury, symptomatic urinary tract infection, history of hematuria, known renal transplant, on maintenance dialysis, participation in any interventional study within past three months and pregnant women were excluded from the study. No study-specific medication was used during the course of the study. The normal treatment, as suggested by the physician, was continued for the patients as a normal routine. The study was performed keeping in check the ethical considerations of the along with keeping in view the technical requirements for the study. ACR was calculated from urine creatinine and albumin, while GFR was estimated by using a modification of diet in renal disease equation:

$$\text{eGFR (mL/min/1.73 m}^2\text{)} = 175 \times (\text{Serum creatinine } [\mu\text{mol/L}])^{-1.154} \times \text{age (years)} - 0.203 \times 0.742 \text{ (if female)}$$

RESULTS

The mean age of the study population was found out to be around 53.5 years. The mean duration of T2DM was 102 months. In the course of data analysis, nearly 43% of the total participants were reported to be affected by dyslipidemia and hypertension. It was studied in the research that a very low percentage of the patients were affected by microvascular and macrovascular complications. It was also found in the study that nearly 720 of the patients suffered from CKD and also had T2DM. Renal dysfunction was found as per eGFR criteria (<60 mL/min/1.73 m²) and UACR criteria (≥30 mg/g) in 24.5% and 36% of study population respectively.

DISCUSSION

In the current study the Renal dysfunction was found as per eGFR criteria (<60 mL/min/1.73 m²) and UACR criteria (≥30 mg/g) in 24.5% and 36% of study population respectively. In the study by Crofford et al. (1999) albuminuria (urinary albumin excretion of > or = 300 mg per 24 hours) by 54 per cent (95 per cent confidence interval 19 to 74 per cent), and that of clinical neuropathy by 60 per cent (95 per cent confidence interval, 38 to 74 per cent). Further, as per the current study, 40% of the study population suffers from CKD. Moreover, recently a large, multicentric international study, SAVOR-TIMI 53 reported that the proportion of patients with eGFR below 50 mL/min/1.73 m² was approximately 18% only despite the average duration of diabetes being ten years. It was also found during the study that early intervention and diagnosis is helpful in better management of the disease.

CONCLUSION

The study adds valuable literature that identifies the level of renal dysfunction in patients suffering from T2DM. It was also analyzed that the majority of the patients having T2DM suffered from chronic kidney disease in India. The study also concluded that with early diagnosis and better management, it is possible to delay the onset of type 2 diabetes at a young age and make it less severe.

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